

Customer's Satisfaction towards E-Banking Services with Special Reference to SBI

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Abstract

Banking is considered as the nerve counter of trade, commerce and business in a country. It plays a vital role in distributing the technological development in the banking sector like information technology, security systems and description models. It has brought significant changes in modern banking service in India. Many value-added services in the banking sector have been introduced to the customer's satisfaction in this competitive field. In the long run, it will have the way for the significant growth in the service sector. E-Banking is conducting ones banking or bank account online through a computer and an internet connection. “Electronic banking is the use of a computer to retrieve and the process of banking data (statement, transaction details) and to initiate transaction directly with a bank or other financial services provide remotely via a telecommunication network.”

Introduction

Online banking also known as internet banking, e-banking or virtual banking, is an electronic payment system that enables a customer of a bank or other financial institution to conduct a range of financial transactions through the financial institution's website. The Online banking system will typically connect to part of the core banking system operated by a bank and is in contrast to branch banking which was the traditional way customers assessed banking service.

History

First Online Banking Services in the United States

Online banking was first introduced in the early 1980s in Newyork, United States. Four Major Banks – Citibank, Chase Manhattan, Chemical Bank, Manufacturers Hanover – offered home banking services. Chemical introduced its Pronto services for individuals and small business in 1983, which enabled individual and small-business clients to maintain electronic checkbooks registers, see account balances and transfer funds between checking and savings accounts. Pronto failed to attract enough customers to break even and was abandoned in 1989. Other banks had a similar experience.

Almost simultaneously with the United States, Online banking arrived in the United Kingdom . The UK's first home online banking services known as the Home link was set by Bank of Scotland for

the customers of the Nottingham Building society (NBS) in 1983. The system was used based on the UK's Prestel view link system used a computer, such as the BBC Micro or keyboard (Tandata Td1400) connected to the telephone system and television set. The system allowed Viewing the statements in Online, banking transfers and bill payment. In order to make bank transfers and bill payments a written instruction giving details of the intended recipient had to be sent to the NBS who set the details up on the Home link systems.

Literature Review

Picado Gonzalez and Eckelman(2004) study on "Customer satisfaction using QFD an e-banking case" Investigated the customer satisfaction using the technique of Quality function Deployment technique framework and it predicted that research on the service quality and customer satisfaction has become highly significant in service industries. Application of CWQ (Customer Window Quadrant) and Action Plan Matrix helps in the analysis of customer and service elements.

Rakesh H M & Ramya TJ (2014) : In their research paper titled "A Study on factors influencing consumer adoption of internet banking in India" tried to examine the factors that influence internet banking adoption using PLS a model is successfully proved and it is found that internet banking is influenced by its perceived reliability, perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. In the marketing process of internet banking services marketing expert should emphasize these benefits its adoption provides and awareness can also be improved to attract consumers attention to internet banking services.

Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of the study are

- To analyze the benefits availed through E-Banking services to its customers by SBI bank
- To analyze the impact of e-banking services on customers.
- To study the factors, those are influencing the bank customers to use e-banking services.
- To give suggestions for decision making.

Research Methodology

Primary data were collected from ninety respondents of bank customers from SBI Bank. The secondary data were collected from published sources like various books, journals, internet website of State Bank of India, etc. The sampling population of this study includes ninety bank customers of SBI bank in Tirunelveli district. Convenience sampling method was used for collecting the data.

Statement of the Problems

The Government is launching many new programmes in the country which are suitable to people's community to meet the objective of countries development one such programme is launching of e-banking services. As the e-banking services have started flourishing in the district in the past few years, the banking organizations have to meet the competition among the banking sector. There is a lack of awareness among the SBI customer's regarding e-banking services through the study has been chosen for the study.

Benefits Availed through E-Banking Services

E-Banking means any user with a personal computer and a browser can get connected to his or her bank's website to perform any of the virtual banking functions. In the E-Banking system, the bank has a centralized data base that is web-enabled. E-Banking provides enormous benefits to consumers regarding withdrawal, checking of balance, transfer of funds, Online information,

bill payment, loan rates, the opening of an account, e-shopping, import-export, downloading of forms, either through internet telephone or other electronic delivery. The benefits availed through E-Banking services to its customers by the SBI bank are analyzed with the help of Garrett's Ranking technique. Ten benefits are given to the respondents and they are ranked as Withdrawal, Checking of balance, Transfer of funds, Online information, Bill payment, Loan rates, Opening of account, E-shopping Imports – Export and Downloading of forms.

Table 1 Benefits through E-Banking services

Sl.No	E-Banking services	Garrett's mean score	Rank
1	Withdrawal	62.74	I
2	Checking of balance	50.74	X
3	Transfer of funds	56.58	III
4	Online information	54.56	V
5	Bill payment	59.57	II
6	Loan rates	51.81	IX
7	Opening of account	52.21	VIII
8	E-Shopping	54.81	IV
9	Import – Export	53.55	VII
10	Downloading of forms	54.4	VI

Source: Primary Data

It is inferred from Table 1 that the main benefit availed through E-Banking services is withdrawal with the mean score of 62.74. The second and third perceived by them are bill payment and transfer of funds with the mean score of 59.57 and 56.58. The fourth and fifth perceived by them are E-Shopping and online information with the mean score of 54.81 and 54.56. The sixth and seventh perceived by them are downloading of forms and import-export with the mean score of 54.4 and 53.55. The eighth and ninth perceived by them are opening of account and loan rates with the mean score of 53.21 and 51.81 and the last benefit perceived by them in checking of balance with the mean score of 50.74.

Impact of E-Banking services on customers

The study deals with the impact of e-banking services to the customers. Totally 14 variables are selected such 24X7 hour service, accessibility, accuracy of transactions, maintenance of records, cost saving, ensure payment in due course, provide secure service, handling of users grievances, communication in regional language, user friendly system, transaction receipt, timely update, queuing time processing time of the respondents who are using e-banking services of SBI bank in Tirunelveli district.

Table 2 Impact of E-Banking services

Sl.No	Variable	SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Total	Mean	Rank
1	24X7 hour services	21	11	19	23	16	268	2.97	XII
2	Accessibility	19	29	12	17	13	598	6.64	I
3	Accuracy of transactions	19	22	16	18	15	586	6.51	II
4	Maintenance of records	31	22	11	12	14	314	3.48	VI
5	Cost savings	23	34	16	9	8	325	3.61	V

6	Ensure payment in due course	39	24	31	9	10	297	3.3	VIII
7	Provide secure service	39	24	10	8	9	346	3.84	III
8	Handling of users grievances	17	19	28	21	5	292	3.24	IX
9	Communication in regional language	26	19	14	14	10	307	3.41	VII
10	User-friendly system	19	22	11	29	9	383	3.14	XI
11	Transaction receipt	34	29	12	9	6	346	3.84	III
12	Timely update	12	17	13	31	17	246	2.73	XIV
13	Quaking time	12	19	23	17	19	258	2.86	XIII
14	Processing time	15	25	21	18	11	285	3.16	X

Source: Primary Data

The above table has the highest score accessibility is the main customer satisfaction with the mean score of 6.64 followed by accuracy of transaction with the mean score of 6.51, transaction receipt and provide secure services with the mean score of 3.84, maintenance of records with the mean score of 3.48 communication in regional language with the mean score of 3.14, ensure payment in due course with the mean score of 3.33, handling of user grievance with the mean score of 3.24, processing time with the mean score of 3.16, user friendly system with the mean score of 3.14, 24X7 hours service with the mean score of 2.97, quaking time with the mean score of 2.86, timely update with the mean score of 2.73.

Findings

- Out of the respondents, the main benefit availed through E-Banking services is withdrawal with the mean score of 62.74.
- Out of the respondents, the highest score accessibility is the main customer satisfaction with a mean score of 6.64.

Suggestions

- The use of technology in banking service enhances the service offering to the customers. The banks must increase their efficiency to provide more efficient services to the customers.
- Banks must take more steps to introduce the e-banking habits among the age group below 25 years. This can be done through the educational institution.
- The banks must take necessary steps to improve the efficiency in the service delivery hence boost up customer's confidence.
- The banks must make the system for payment of electricity bill, payment of telephone bill, payment of tax, etc., very simple that an ordinary man can find it easy to handle e-banking services.

Conclusion

Electronic banking has become a necessary survival weapon and is fundamentally changing the banking industry worldwide. Today, the click of a mouse offers bank customer's services at a much lower cost and also empowers them with unprecedented freedom in choosing vendors for their financial service needs. Banks have to upgrade and constantly think of new innovative, customized package and services to remain competitive. A lost need to be done to create confidence in the minds of customers about the benefits and security of the e-banking services. There is a need for total satisfaction with all the quality of nature of e-banking services and different models of services.

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